

Research

Improving Railway Safety with AI: Detecting Defective Fasteners using Deep Learning

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Abstract: Railway track inspection is a vital task to ensure safe and efficient train travel. However, traditional inspection methods require people to walk along the tracks and look for issues, which is time-consuming and exhausting. To address this, we created a new system that uses a camera installed under a train to take pictures of the tracks automatically. Then, we applied advanced computer methods like YOLO (You Only Look Once), SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector), and ResNet50 (Residual Network50) to analyze the images and identify any areas that need fixing.

ResNet50 is a type of computer network that can recognize patterns in pictures, and we used it to enhance the performance of the other two methods. Our system achieved an average detection rate of 99%, meaning that it can identify track anomalies as accurately as a human operator but much faster.

This new system has several benefits over traditional methods, such as increasing efficiency and accuracy, minimizing human involvement, and reducing operational costs. By improving safety and reducing the risk of accidents, this technology has the potential to revolutionize the railway maintenance industry.

In summary, our study presents a new automated technique for detecting rail anomalies using computer vision and deep learning-based methods. This technology can help make train travel safer and more efficient, ultimately benefiting both passengers and railway companies.

Keywords: railway track inspection, computer vision, deep learning, SSD, ResNet50, YOLO, automated detection

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Introduction

With the continuous growth of the world economy, railway transportation plays a more and more important role in the economic lifeline. In order to meet the growing demand for economic development, railway construction has also increased year by year. Railway track is composed of several key parts, such as sleeper, rail, and fastener. As the connecting part of fixed track and sleeper, track fastener is an important part to ensure the safety of railway operation. Huge safety risks and even major accidents were caused by the defective track fasteners, such as breaks or missing.

Defective track fastener is caused by the contact friction and vibration impact between the hub and the track, as well as the impact of the natural environment [1, 2].

Currently, track fasteners are mainly detected through manual inspection, which is inefficient and can introduce uncontrollable risk factors such as missed or false inspections. With the rapid development of automation technology [3–6], manual inspection methods are no longer adequate to meet the demands of modern railway transit. Automating the track fastener detection technology [7, 8] is significant to track operation and maintenance. However, the existing track fastener defect detection methods are limited, and the detection accuracy is low. In recent years, with the rapid development of artificial intelligence technology [9, 10], image processing methods based on deep learning have become a research hotspot [11–13]. Deep learning networks have achieved important research results in image classification [14, 15].

The defect detection method of track fastener based on deep learning avoids complicated feature extraction. The manual design and selection of image features are replaced by automatic extraction of image features by computer. The deep learning network automatically learns the pattern recognition system of features from the data set, and the information in the image can be extracted more comprehensively [16]. Although the feature extraction of deep learning is shown to be far superior to traditional “artificial design features,” the existing track fastener defect detection network based on deep learning is a supervised network, and a large amount of labeled sample data is required for a supervised network. For example, when using convolutional neural networks to detect defects in track fasteners [17], a large number of labeled training sample images are required. However, the actual situation is that the number of abnormal samples of track fastener is rare, which is limited for the establishment of supervised learning model.

Because the supervised network is limited by the number of abnormal fastener images, it is difficult to establish, so the unsupervised network is adopted. However, different deep learning networks have different structure and depth. With different deep learning networks, the features of track fastener image are extracted differently, and the detection ability of different features is also different. The feature information of track fastener image extracted by single network is not comprehensive enough, and the feature information of track fastener image cannot be used well. For example, the edge feature of the track fastener image is extracted [18–20]. Edge feature is an important feature of image, and image edge is the discontinuity of image features such as pixel gray distribution. Image edge is the set of pixels whose characteristics around the image change step or ridge. The edge extraction is mainly to retain the sharply changed area of the image, and the contour edge of the track fastener can be obtained. The edge contour feature of the track fastener image is helpful to distinguish the state of track fastener loss and track fastener clip loosening. The texture feature of track fastener is extracted [21–23]. The image texture feature is a global feature, and the visual features of homogeneity in the image are reflected. The arrangement properties of the surface structure of the object surface with slow or periodic changes are reflected. The texture feature can effectively represent the clip detail feature of track fastener image, and the clip detail feature of track fastener image is helpful to identify the fracture state of track fastener clip. These features are not well integrated and utilized at the same time, and the feature information of track fastener image is not fully expressed, which leads to a high rate of missing alarm in track fastener defect detection [24–26].

Since, for SKL and Vossloh fasteners, the track fastener picture is composed of the track fastener clip subimage and the track fastener mono subimage, the track fastener's defect is mainly determined by the state of the track fastener clip subimage.

The proposed method for defect classification of fasteners

In this project, we propose to develop an effective vision-based automatic rail inspection system. The primary objective of this system is to detect the presence of parts of interest in rail tracks, such as fasteners, by inspecting real images acquired by a digital camera installed under a diagnostic train.

Residual Network (ResNet)

Residual Network (ResNet) is a deep learning model used for computer vision applications. It is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture designed to support hundreds or thousands of convolutional layers. Previous CNN architectures were not able to scale to a large number of layers, which resulted in limited performance. However, when adding more layers, researchers faced the “vanishing gradient” problem.

ResNet is a type of computer program that can "see" images, and it's really good at it! It uses a special kind of math called neural networks to recognize things in pictures. But, there was a problem with earlier programs like ResNet - they couldn't be made very big, or they wouldn't work as well. This was because of something called the "vanishing gradient" problem, which is like a math hiccup that slows down the learning process.

To solve this problem, the creators of ResNet came up with a clever idea called "skip connections". Basically, ResNet adds extra connections between different parts of the program, so that the math doesn't get bogged down. This makes the program much faster and more accurate! ResNet was developed in 2016 by introducing some features that significantly increase network accuracy and speed [27].

One of the cool things about ResNet is that it doesn't have to use all of its "neurons" (little math units) at once. Once it learns how to recognize something, it can focus on learning new things instead. This is like how people can remember things they learned in school and then learn new things later.

ResNet is really good at recognizing all kinds of things in pictures, like animals, cars, and buildings. In fact, it's so good that it's used by a lot of different programs and websites! The ResNet50 network consists of 50 layers, and its architecture is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: ResNet50 architecture

When training any pretrained network, we start by modifying the parameters of the basic design. In each of the CNN models, we tuned the pretrained network parameters, i.e., the convolution 2D layer and the classification output layer. We modified the filter size to 1×1 , and the number of filters to 2 as we had two classes of data. We modified the classification output layer to suit our output classification and labels. Furthermore, we set the starting learning rate to 0.0001, the validation frequency to 5, and the maximum epochs to 60, since we wanted to avoid the failure of training pauses based on error rates. An epoch is a single learning cycle in which the learner is exposed to the whole training dataset. Furthermore, the minimum batch size is equal to 11, which corresponds to the memory needs (8.00 GB) of the CPU hardware, which operates at 1.8 GHz. Increasing the number of epochs leads to better training and validation accuracy, but it may lead to overfitting. The training dataset was randomly separated into two parts: 70% of the data for training and 30% of the data for validation to avoid overfitting.

In this article, we will focus on the SSD object detection algorithm and show you how to use the TensorFlow Object Detection API to develop your own detection network.

Single Shot Multibox Detector (SSD)

An SSD network has two main parts: a backbone model and an SSD head. The backbone is usually a fancy neural network trained on big image datasets, while the SSD head is a few extra layers that come after the backbone. The SSD head helps the network figure out where objects are in an image by guessing at their size and location. This is done by predicting how far away an object is from a set of pre-designed boxes of different sizes and shapes, and how confident the network is that the object is really there. You can see an example of these boxes in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: An SSD model structure that adds several feature layers to the end of a base network

SSD solution deployment using the API

Using pretrained models as an SSD backbone eases the training process but puts constraints on the network structure. To enable efficient inference on the edge, we need to train a custom CNN solution for applications such as infrared human detection that only require a small backbone model with a relatively restricted number of parameters.

API model structure

At a high level, detection models receive input images and predict output tensors. At training time, output tensors are directly passed to a specified loss function while at evaluation time, they are passed to the post processing function, which converts the raw outputs into actual bounding boxes. The Object Detection API follows this structure. The model you want to train should include the five functions below:

- Preprocess applies any preprocessing operation to the input image tensor. This could include transformations for data augmentation or input normalization.
- Predict produces the model's raw predictions that are passed to the corresponding loss or post processing functions (e.g., Non-Maximum Suppression).
- Postprocess converts raw prediction tensors into appropriate detection results (e.g., bounding box index and offset, class scores, etc.).
- Loss defines a loss function that calculates scalar loss tensors over the provided ground truth.
- Restore loads checkpoints into the TensorFlow graph.

The SSD meta-architecture API

An SSD meta-architecture (SSDMetaArch) requires a feature extractor (SSDFeatureExtractor) to automatically construct appropriate class and offset prediction layers according to the configuration parameters (i.e., number of classes, scales, and aspect ratios). The general framework is summarized in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: SSD detectionModel construction framework

Experimental results

The performance of this system is evaluated in accordance with a scientific methodology based on test results.

(a) Input image.

(b) Output image.

Fig. 4: Input image and output image of the system

(a) Input image.

(b) Output image.

Fig. 5: Input image and output image of the system

Fig. 4, Fig. 5 illustrates what the system should achieve. The system automatically detects the locations of the fasteners in an input rail track image, and displays them in an output image. The average recognition rate reaches 99%. The detection time is 13.6 seconds. The results show that the designed algorithm can meet the needs of the subject.

Conclusion

In summary, the proposed fastener detection model showed better performance compared to previous state-of-the-art models. Existing deep learning-based methods are mainly focused on detecting healthy fasteners and may not work as well for detecting defective or missing ones due to the lack of training data. In the future, researchers aim to improve the training data balance by using generative deep learning techniques to create more data for defective and missing fasteners under different lighting conditions. This could help to enhance the model's ability to detect defective fasteners in real-world scenarios. Overall, this study shows promising results for the use of deep learning in fastener detection, with potential applications in various industries such as manufacturing, construction, and transportation.

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